

AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON THE *PRĀKṚTA GUṆA KARMA* OF *VĀTA DOṢA* AND THEIR PATHOLOGICAL VARIATIONS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO *VĀTAVYĀDHI* IN *CARAKA SAṂHITĀ*

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ABSTRACT

Vāta Doṣa, among the *Tridoṣas*, holds a pivotal role in *Āyurveda*, regulating bodily functions and maintaining homeostasis. According to *Maharṣi Caraka*, *Vāta* is the essence of life, responsible for sustaining strength and integrity of the body. Its normal functioning is determined by *prakṛta guṇa-karma* (natural qualities and actions), while deviations lead to pathological conditions collectively termed *Vātavyādhi*. Despite its clinical significance, interpretation of *Vāta*'s *guṇa-karma* and their pathological variations remains underexplored. This dissertation presents an exploratory study of the *prakṛta guṇa-karma* of *Vāta Doṣa*, as described in classical texts—primarily *Caraka Saṁhitā*—and investigates their pathological alterations in various *Vātavyādhi*. By critically analyzing derangements of *Vāta guṇa-karma* and incorporating expert perspectives, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive

understanding to inform precise diagnostic and therapeutic strategies grounded in *guṇa-siddhānta*. **Study Design:** Conceptual and qualitative research integrating classical textual analysis with in-depth interviews of domain experts.

Objectives

1. To examine the *prakṛta guṇa-karma* of *Vāta Doṣa* and its role in physiological balance.
2. To analyze pathological variations of *Vāta guṇa-karma* in *Vātavyādhi* described in *Caraka Saṁhitā*.

Pathogenesis of *Vatavyādhi* is essentially the pathological expression of *Vāta guṇas* and its *Karma*. For example:

- Excess *Rūkṣa* and *Śīta* → joint stiffness, dryness.
- Aggravated *Cala* → tremors, spasms, instability.
- Distorted *Sūkṣma* → neurological and cognitive dysfunction.

Thus, *guṇa-vikṛti* forms the core of disease manifestation. Ayurveda prescribes *cikitsā* through *sāmānya-viśeṣa siddhānta*, where antagonistic qualities restore balance.

Despite detailed textual references, systematic analysis of *guṇa-karma* in *Vatavyādhi* is limited in contemporary Ayurveda research. This study bridges that gap by exploring *guṇa-karma* variations in *Vatavyādhi* through literary analysis and expert opinion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Conceptual and qualitative research.

Sources of Data

- Primary texts: *Caraka Saṃhitā*, *Suśruta Saṃhitā*, *Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya*, *Aṣṭāṅga Saṅgraha*, *Bhela Saṃhitā*, *Kāśyapa Saṃhitā*.
- Commentaries: *Cakrapāṇi*, *Dalhaṇa*, *Aruṇadatta*, *Mādhukośa*.
- Secondary sources: *Nighantus*, modern research articles.

Exclusions: Conditions involving *āvaraṇa* and *gatavāta* were excluded to maintain clarity in analyzing primary *Vātavyādhi*.

Expert Opinion

- Semi-structured questionnaire developed from textual findings.
- In-depth interviews conducted with highly experienced Ayurveda clinicians in the field of *Vātavyādhi* management using snowball sampling.
- Responses analyzed thematically and represented with charts and tables.

Data Analysis

- Literary data presented descriptively.
- Expert consensus findings plotted as frequency distributions of *guṇa* and *karma* in each *Vātavyādhi*.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Analysis was carried out for 11 *Vātavyādhi* mentioned in *Caraka Saṃhitā*: *Ardita*, *Antarāyāma*, *Bahirāyāma*, *Hanugraha*, *Ākṣēpaka*, *Dandaka*, *Pakṣāghāta*, *Ekāṅgavāta*, *Sarvāṅgavāta*, *Gridhrasī*, and *Khallī*.

Symptom-based analysis of *guṇa* and *karma vikṛti* in 11 *Vatavyādhis* as per expert opinion

Ardita.^[10]

In *Ardita*, the expert-based analysis of symptom-wise *guṇa* and *karma vikṛti* highlights a clear predominance of *cala* and *rūkṣa guṇas*, alongside *ceṣṭā karma vikṛti*, forming the core pathogenic triad.

The *cala guṇa* reflects the involuntary movements, such as sudden muscle twitches and asymmetrical facial expressions, indicating excessive instability of *Vāta*. *Rūkṣa guṇa*, on the other hand, signifies the dryness and lack of lubrication in the facial tissues, resulting in stiffness, impaired articulation, and a characteristic loss of *snigdhatva*. These two *guṇas*, when aggravated, disturb the natural flow and stability of *Vāta* in the *śira-mukha sthāna*.

Laghu and *śīta guṇas* were also found to contribute to the clinical picture—*laghu* through *dhātu kṣaya* (evidenced by facial thinning and weakness) and *śīta* by promoting *stambha*(rigidity) and *saṅkocha* (constriction), especially affecting the sensory components. *Sūkṣma guṇa*, though minimally expressed, was acknowledged for facilitating subtle invasion of *Vāta* into minute *śrotasas*.

On the *karma* side, *ceṣṭā* was universally impaired, denoting motor dysfunction and loss of voluntary control over facial musculature. Secondary dysfunctions included *dhātugati* and *indriya pāṭava*, reflecting deeper tissue and sensory involvement. Thus, *Ardita* emerges as a *cala-rūkṣa-ceṣṭā vikṛti pradhāna* condition with *laghu-śīta-sūkṣma guṇa & dhātu gati-indriya pāṭava karma vikṛti anubandha*.

Antarāyāma^[11]

In *Antarāyāma*, *rūkṣa* was unanimously identified, followed by *cala*, *śīta*, *khara* and *sūkṣma*. The dominance of *rūkṣa* indicates loss of lubrication, leading to rigidity, while *cala* reflects spasmodic and uncontrolled movement. *Cala guṇa* was a frequently observed *guṇa* across the

Antarāyāma lakṣaṇas, signifying that disturbed or exaggerated movement is a key pathogenic feature in this condition. It was the sole dominant *guṇa* in cases like *Prṣṭa ākṣepa*.

Śīta contributed to *stambha*(stiffness), and *sūkṣma* pointed to subtle neuro-muscular involvement.

Khara guṇa, though less frequent, was observed especially in rigid conditions like *Vadanāsaṅga* and *grīvā stambha*, reinforcing its connection with rough, immobile stiffness.

The sole *karma* affected across all symptoms was *ceṣṭā*, highlighting profound impairment of voluntary motion. This portrays *Antarayāma* as a primarily *rūkṣa–cala–ceṣṭā* disorder with additional *śīta–sūkṣma–khara* involvement. Even with minimal involvement, *laghu guṇa* is also considered significant in this context.

***Bahirāyāma*^[12]**

Cala guṇa shows maximum involvement (present in almost every *lakṣaṇa*), highlighting *Vāta*'s mobile nature. *Rūkṣa* and *Śīta* are also consistently observed, supporting their classical role in *Vāta prakopa*. *Khara*, *sūkṣma* and *laghu* were also prominent, reflecting stiffness and finer neurovascular involvement. While *Jāta Vēgam nihanti* includes all *guṇas*, showing complete functional suppression of *Vāta karma*, the universal and consistent dysfunction was *ceṣṭā*, denoting disturbed voluntary and involuntary motion. Hence, *Bahirāyāma* represents a state of extensive *cala–rūkṣa–śīta* derangement, with *ceṣṭā* impairment as the clinical core.

***Hanugraha*^[13]**

In *Hanugraha*, *Cala* and *Śīta guṇa* are universally involved (present in all symptoms), affirming their role in movement regulation and motor disturbances. *Rūkṣa* is also commonly involved, indicating the association of dryness contributing to stiffness and locking of the jaw whereas in case of pathology related to *Hanubandha sramsā*, the *guṇa* predominantly affected were *cala*, *rūkṣa* and *laghu*, producing *sramsā* (loosened jaw). The principal karma impaired was *ceṣṭā*, especially of orofacial muscles, indicating restricted functional movement. Also, *Vega pravartana*(*Jrmbha*) was identified as affected by eight experts, indicating its clinical relevance in *Hanugraha*. *Hanugraha* thus highlights how *cala guṇa* along with *rūkṣa* and *śīta* combine to produce localized *stambha*, with *ceṣṭā* impairment as the clinical outcome.

***Ākṣēpaka*^[14]**

Experts unanimously recognized *cala* as the defining *guṇa*, directly correlating with violent, involuntary movements. *Rūkṣa* and *laghu* were equally acknowledged, supporting drying-induced instability and loss of strength. Unlike other disorders, *guṇa* like *śīta*, *khara*, and *sūkṣma* were not considered central, pointing to a more kinetic, surface-level pathology. In terms of *karma*, *ceṣṭā* was unanimously disturbed, making *Ākṣepaka* a quintessential *cala-rūkṣa-laghu-ceṣṭā* disorder.

***Dandaka*^[15]**

In *Daṇḍaka*, the experts identified a composite picture of *cala hāni*, *rūkṣa*, and *śīta*. Unlike *Ākṣepaka*, where excess mobility dominates, *Daṇḍaka* illustrates blocked or arrested mobility, manifesting as *daṇḍavat stabdhatā* and rigidity of *pāṇi*, *pāda*, *śira*, and *pṛṣṭha*. The pathogenic basis lies in loss of *snigdhatā* and *ushṇatā*, causing stiffness, *stambha*, and immobilization. The predominant *karma* affected was *ceṣṭā*, establishing *Daṇḍaka* as a condition of *cala-hāni* with *rūkṣa-śīta* overlay leading to *ceṣṭā-hāni*.

***Pakṣāghāta, Ekāṅgavāta, Sarvāṅgavāta*^[16]**

The *guṇa* most frequently cited was *cala*, followed by *rūkṣa* and *śīta*. This reflects the drying and destabilizing pathology underlying hemiplegic weakness and paralysis. *Śīta* was noted by 16 experts, pointing to coldness and rigidity, while other *guṇa* were less emphasized. Predominant *karma* affected was *ceṣṭā*, highlighting gross motor impairment. *Indriya pātava* was also reported, suggesting impaired tissue nutrition and conduction. *Pakṣavādha* thus emerges as a *cala-rūkṣa-śīta* dominant condition, primarily disabling *ceṣṭā* & *indriya pātava*. *Ekāṅgaroga* is a localized expression of the same *cala-rūkṣa-śīta-ceṣṭā* pathology seen in *Pakṣavādha*, but restricted to one limb or region. *Sarvāṅgaroga* is a globalized manifestation of *cala-rūkṣa-śīta* pathology affecting both motion and sensory coordination all over the body.

***Grdhrāsī*^[17]**

In this condition, *cala* and *rūkṣa* were most frequent, followed by *śīta*. The predominance of *cala* points to radiating pain and abnormal mobility, while *rūkṣa* produces tissue depletion and dryness in *snāyu* and *asthidhatu*. The *karma* affected was predominantly *ceṣṭā*, manifesting as limping gait and impaired leg movement. *Gridhrasī* is therefore a *cala-rūkṣa-śīta-ceṣṭā* disorder with neuromuscular emphasis.

Khallī^[18]

Khallī displayed a similar profile, with *rūkṣa* and *laghu* as major *guṇa*, producing neuromuscular weakness and pain. *Śīta* was also noted, along with lesser *cala* involvement. The primary *lakṣaṇa*, *Pāda, Jaṅghā, Ūru, Kara-mūla avamotanī*, reflects a pathological state marked by excessive dryness and disturbed mobility. The primary *karma* disturbed was *ceṣṭā*, with some experts also acknowledging *dhātu gati* derangement. This confirms Khallī as a localized degenerative *rūkṣa-laghu-ceṣṭā* condition.

Table 1: Disease specific Distribution of *Guṇa* and *Karma vikṛti* in different *Vātavyādhi* as per expert opinion.

<i>Disease</i>	<i>Dominantly affected Guṇa</i>	<i>Dominantly affected Karma</i>
<i>Ardita</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Laghu, Śīta, Sūkṣma</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa, Indriya Patava, Dhātu Samyak Gati, Vēga Pravartana</i>
<i>Antarāyāma</i>	<i>Rūkṣa, Cala, Śīta, Khara, Sūkṣma</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa, Dhātu Samyak Gati, Vēga Pravartana</i>
<i>Bahirāyāma</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Śīta, Khara, Sūkṣma</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa, Dhātu Samyak Gati, Vēga Pravartana</i>
<i>Hanugraha</i>	<i>Hanugraha :- Cala, Śīta Rūkṣa, Hanusrams:- Cala, Rūkṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa</i>
<i>Ākṣēpaka</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa, Dhātu Samyak Gati</i>
<i>Daṇḍaka</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Śīta</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa</i>
<i>Pakṣāghāta, Sarvāṅgavāta & Ekāṅgavāta</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Śīta</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa, Indriya Patava</i>
<i>Gridhrasi</i>	<i>Cala, Rūkṣa, Śīta</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa</i>
<i>Khalli</i>	<i>Rūkṣa, Laghu</i>	<i>Cēṣṭa</i>

DISCUSSION

The present study offers an in-depth analysis of the deranged *guṇa* and *karma* of *Vāta doṣa* in various *Vātavyādhis*, based on expert opinions and classical references, with the aim of bridging traditional understanding with clinical manifestations. This exploration emphasizes the diagnostic and therapeutic significance of recognizing *guṇa-karma* pathology in individual *Vātavyādhi* entities and their symptoms.

The findings reaffirm the primacy of *Vāta guṇa-karma* in both physiology and pathology.

1. Normal vs. Pathological States

In the *prākṛta* state, *Vāta guṇas* sustain vital functions, whereas in *vikṛti* they manifest as disease. For example, in a healthy state, *cala guṇa* governs *preraṇa karma*, which initiates all forms of movement in the body. When deranged (*cala vikṛti*), however, it produces specific

pathologies: *cala* vṛddhi leads to tremors as seen in *akṣepaka*; *cala* hāni produces rigidity as in *daṇḍaka* or immobility as in *pakṣāghāta* etc. Various pathological states such as vṛddhi and hāni of specific Vāta guṇas give rise to different types of disorders, all grouped under the broad category of Vātavyādhi.

2. Dominant Guṇa–karma in Vātavyādhi

- *Cala* guṇa emerged as the most critical factor in Vātavyādhi, reaffirming that this group of Vāta-origin disorders is chiefly characterized by *cala* guṇa vikāra and *ceṣṭā* karma vaikalya.
- Behind the pathological variations of *cala* guṇa lie etiological factors that provoke *rūkṣa* and *śīta* guṇa of Vāta, leading to *stambha* and thereby disturbing the normal *gati* of *vāyu* (*cala* guṇa and *ceṣṭā* karma).
- Thus, *rūkṣa* and *śīta* guṇa are secondarily involved in the clinical manifestations of the majority of Vātavyādhis.
- *Khara* and *laghu* act as additional aggravating factors, supporting the actions of *rūkṣa* and *śīta* in producing *ceṣṭā* vaikalya and causing Vātavyādhi.
- Their varying degrees of involvement, in different combinations and in different *sthānas*, result in distinct conditions such as *ardita*, *pakṣāghāta*, and *hanugraha*.
- The role of *sūkṣma* guṇa in *ardita*, *antarāyāma*, and *bahirayāma* highlights the subtlety of *vāyu* in disturbing both *ceṣṭā* karma and *indriya* paṭava karma.
- Derangement of *guṇas* directly leads to impairment of *karmas*, making *guṇa*-vikṛti the substratum of *karma*-vikṛti.
- In *daṇḍaka*, an *asādhyā* vyādhi, all *vāyu* *karmas* are progressively impaired, ultimately leading to *maraṇa* or death.

3. Relevance in Cikitsa

Understanding *guṇa* dominance provides clear therapeutic direction.

A. Therapy selection

- Rūkṣa* imbalance → *snigdha* therapies (*snehana*, *basti*).
- Śīta* imbalance → *uṣṇa* treatments (*svedana*, *uṣṇa* *dravya*).
- Cala* imbalance → stabilizing approaches (*snigdha* *uṣṇa* *anulomana*).
- Laghu* imbalance → nourishing therapies (*bṛmhaṇa*).

B. Dravya selection

Numerous *vāta-hara dravyas* (single herbs and formulations) are described in the classics. By analyzing the dominant *guṇa-karma* involved, one can select the most appropriate drug of choice through the principle of *sāmānya-viśeṣa siddhānta*, while also considering factors such as *doṣa* and *sthāna*.

4. Modern Correlations

Several neurological and degenerative disorders—such as Parkinson’s disease, paralysis, and osteoarthritis—closely correspond to *Vātavyādhi*. A *guṇa*-based understanding enhances Ayurveda’s role in integrative medicine.

CONCLUSION

This exploratory literary study demonstrates that the pathological essence of *Vātavyādhi* lies in the derangement of *Vāta’s guṇa-karma*. The predominance of *cala guṇa* and *ceṣṭā karma vaikalya* emerges as central in most conditions.

By emphasizing the diagnostic and therapeutic significance of *guṇa* analysis, the study underscores the continuing relevance of *guṇa-siddhānta* in Ayurveda. This framework bridges classical knowledge with modern clinical challenges, offering a precise and practical approach to the management of neuromuscular and degenerative disorders.

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